

Some New Applications of Surface-Tension and Parachor etc. distinguishing between Isomers

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Possibilities of application of surface tension, Parachor and conductivity data, to distinguish between geometric and position isomers have been suggested in the light of following criteria.

Equimolar aqueous and non-aqueous solutions of the isomers having different dissociation constants and different strengths and extents of H-bonding should show different extents of drops in parachor.

It is found that equimolar aqueous solutions of maleic and fumaric acids have relatively (a) larger surface tensions, (b) lower conductivities, (c) higher densities and (d) larger parachor values, while their non-aqueous solutions show relatively (a) larger surface tensions, (b) smaller conductivities, (c) larger densities and (d) larger parachor values in the case of fumaric acid. In the case of equimolar non-aqueous solutions of position isomers like (*o*, *m*, *p*) nitro, hydroxy and amino benzoic acids, parachor values are in the order ortho < meta < para.

In all the above cases, gradations obtained in the case of various data are shown to give an idea regarding distinction between various isomers.

Besides the use of chemical methods, various physical properties like m.p., dissociation constants, dipole moments etc., have been employed to distinguish between the geometric and position isomers.¹

So far as parachor is concerned, atomic and structural units constituting the molecules of the above two isomers are identical, calculated parachor value of the two acids must, therefore, be identical. The same is true for the disubstituted benzene isomers like *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-hydroxy benzoic acids etc., also. Hence at the first sight it appears that parachor cannot be used as a method to distinguish between the isomers. Sugden² was also of the similar opinion. He could not find any gradation in the parachor values of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-isomers and attributed the experimentally observed small differences in values to the experimental errors.

Buehler, Clemens and Gardner³, however, for the first time, showed that the effect of temperature on parachor values of disubstituted position isomers of benzene, capable of H-bond formation, can help in distinguishing an *o*- compound from its *m*- and *p*- isomers. They studied the effect of temperature on pure compounds only. They were unable to put forth a general criterion for distinguishing between *o*-, *m*- and *p*- isomers.

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2. Sugden, Parachor and Valency; Routledge, London (1930), Edn.; appendix.

3. Buehler, Gardner and Clemens, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 2, 168.

From the foregoing discussion based on a careful survey of the literature, it appears that Parachor has hitherto not been applied as a criterion to distinguish between geometric isomers and position isomers respectively amongst themselves. Although an attempt⁴ has been made by us from different angles to use parachor for distinction between position isomers, in the present paper-series following view points have been applied to the problem of isomerism in general.

It has been established that there occurs a drop in parachor (a) due to ionisation⁵⁻⁶ and also (b) due to H-bonding.⁷⁻¹¹ Since there occurs a drop in parachor due to ionisation, if equimolar solutions of isomers are prepared in the same solvent (preferably water) the drop in parachor value will be more in the case of substance undergoing ionisation to a greater extent. Thus the observations on relative drops in parachor due to ionisation obtained from such solutions should help in distinguishing the isomers, provided their ionisation constants differ appreciably.

The extent of drop in parachor due to H-bonding depends upon the nature of the solvent, solute, concentration and temperature, as has been shown⁴. Hence if equimolar solutions of isomers are prepared in the same non-ionising solvents and are studied at the same temperature, parachor values for solute isomers obtained, should vary, depending upon the nature of the solute. These have, therefore, been tested.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of either A.R. or B.D.H. quality. Conductivity water was used for the preparation of aqueous solutions. Surface tensions were determined, using Jaeger's well-known maximum bubble pressure method. An ASCO cathetometer of 0.001 cms. accuracy was used to take manometer readings and to find the depth of the capillary in the experimental liquids. Springel type pycnometer was used to find the densities of the liquids. Solutions were thermostated at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ during the determinations. Parachor values of solutes were obtained by using Hammic and Andrew's¹² method. Phillip's conductivity bridge was used to determine conductivities

RESULTS

In the following tables the notations have the meaning as : Mal. = Maleic acid, fum. = fumaric acid, x = molar fraction of the solute, d_m = density of the mixture, r_m = Surface tension of the mixture, P_s = Parachor of the solute.

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Section 1 :—Geometric Isomers in aqueous solutions.

TABLE 1

Maleic and Fumaric acids in water

$X \times 10^3$	d_m		r_m	
	Mal.	Fum.	Mal.	Fum.
0.2497	.9956	.9962	71.25	71.45
0.2181	.9957	.9962	71.32	71.52
0.1866	.9960	.9963	71.52	71.56
0.1555	.9961	.9966	71.56	71.78
0.1245	.9963	.9967	71.71	71.85

TABLE 2

Maleic and Fumaric acids in water

$X \times 10^3$	P_s		Sp. Cond. $\times 10^3$ mhos	
	Mal.	Fum.	Mal.	Fum.
0.2497	190.0	200.0	8.5	2.1
0.2181	191.1	200.2	5.4	2.0
0.1866	193.2	202.0	5.1	1.8
0.1555	195.3	203.5	4.2	1.6
0.1245	197.5	205.6	3.6	1.4

Section 2 :—Geometric isomers in non-aqueous solutions.

TABLE 1

Maleic and Fumaric acids in Ethyl alcohol

$X \times 10^3$	d_m		r_m	
	Mal.	Fum.	Mal.	Fum.
0.6952	.7991	.8054	23.57	23.84
0.6019	.7075	.8041	23.44	22.68
0.5015	.7967	.8036	23.35	22.57
0.4011	.7960	.8032	22.31	22.49
0.3079	.7031	.7991	22.82	22.16

TABLE 2

Maleic and Fumaric acids in Ethyl alcohol

$X \times 10^3$	P_s		Sp. Cond. $\times 10^5$ mhos	
	Mal.	Fum.	Mal.	Fum.
0.6952	233.4	234.6	8.5	1.9
0.6019	233.0	234.0	7.6	1.9
0.5015	233.8	234.2	7.0	1.8
0.4011	234.0	234.4	6.3	1.7
0.3079	234.5	235.5	5.8	1.6

TABLE 3

Maleic and Fumaric acids in Ethyl Acetate

$X \times 10^2$	d_m		r_m	
	Fum.	Mal.	Fum.	Mal.
0.06850	0.8890	0.8885	23.68	23.73
0.1024	0.8895	0.8888	23.92	23.99
0.1368	0.8912	0.8892	23.95	24.18
0.1708	0.8931	0.8904	24.05	24.35
0.2049	0.8942	0.8909	24.10	24.45

TABLE 4

Fumaric and Maleic acids in Ethyl acetate

$X \times 10^2$	P_s		Sp. Cond. $\times 10^8$ mhos	
	Fum.	Mal.	Fum.	Mal.
0.06850	226.8	222.3	5.6	20.0
0.1024	226.1	221.9	6.0	28.0
0.1368	225.0	221.4	7.0	35.0
0.1708	224.3	221.1	8.0	39.0
0.2049	224.3	221.2	8.7	46.0

Section 3 :—Position Isomers in non aqueous solutions.

TABLE 1

Isomeric (o, m, p) Hydroxy benzoic acids in Ethyl alcohol

$X \times 10^4$	d_m			r_m		
	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -
0.2075	.8152	.8174	.8140	23.46	23.79	23.37
0.1661	.8114	.8128	.8090	23.27	23.48	23.05
0.1255	.8078	.8092	.8019	23.09	23.27	23.01
0.08533	.8035	.8042	.8024	22.87	22.97	22.74
0.04200	.7985	.7990	.7991	22.59	22.63	22.32

TABLE 2

Isomeric (o, m, p) Hydroxy benzoic acids in Ethyl alcohol

$X \times 10^4$	P_s			Sp. Cond. $\times 10^5$ mhos		
	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -
0.2075	290.0	292.5	294.1	7.2	2.8	1.1
0.1661	290.5	293.0	294.5	6.5	2.5	1.0
0.1255	290.2	292.8	294.2	6.1	2.3	0.9
0.08533	291.0	293.0	294.3	4.8	1.8	0.8
0.04200	291.5	293.7	294.7	3.0	1.1	0.7

TABLE 3

Isomeric (o, m, p) Amino benzoic acids in Ethyl acetate

$X \times 10^3$	d_m			r_m		
	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -
0.7214	.8940	.8954	.9008	24.47	24.63	25.23
0.5042	.8932	.8951	.8999	24.41	24.60	25.14
0.4384	.8926	.8947	.8989	24.34	24.55	25.02
0.3121	.8919	.8914	.8978	24.28	24.50	24.94
0.1431	.8911	.8932	.8960	24.18	24.43	24.73

TABLE 4

Isomeric (o, m, p) Amino benzoic acids in Ethyl acetate

$X \times 10^3$	P_s			Sp. Cond. $\times 10^9$ mhos		
	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -
0.7214	295.1	300.8	303.2	5.5	5.0	2.60
0.6042	295.5	301.5	303.5	5.0	4.0	2.35
0.4384	296.0	301.0	304.3	4.4	3.3	2.10
0.3121	297.3	301.8	304.0	3.2	2.43	1.60
0.1431	296.7	302.4	304.7	2.3	1.10	0.80

TABLE 5

Isomeric (o, m, p)-Nitro benzoic acids in Ethyl methyl ketone

$X \times 10^1$	d_m			r_m		
	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -
0.1076	0.8063	0.8098	0.8060	23.79	24.23	23.79
0.1343	0.8078	0.8112	0.8078	23.81	24.25	23.85
0.1607	0.8110	0.8145	0.8102	24.01	24.57	23.99
0.1892	0.8134	0.8191	0.8123	24.12	24.89	24.02
0.1910	0.8154	0.8218	0.8142	24.21	25.02	24.12

TABLE 6

Isomeric (o, m, p)-Nitro benzoic acids in Ethyl methyl ketone

$X \times 10^1$	P_s			Sp. Cond. $\times 10^6$ muos		
	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -	<i>o</i> -	<i>m</i> -	<i>p</i> -
0.1076	324.0	331.2	333.0	3.6	1.9	1.3
0.1343	324.2	331.8	332.7	4.6	2.2	1.4
0.1607	323.4	330.6	332.0	5.2	2.6	1.7
0.1892	322.6	329.7	332.0	5.95	3.05	1.8
0.1910	322.7	329.4	331.2	7.0	3.6	2.0

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Section 1. Geometric Isomers in aqueous solutions : It is clear from the Table 1 and 2 for equimolar aqueous solutions of maleic and fumaric acids that,

- (i) these substances decrease the surface tension of water with their increasing concentrations
- (ii) Surface tension values in the case of fumaric acid solutions are higher than those for the corresponding maleic acid solutions, for a given concentration.
- (iii) Conductivities of maleic acid solutions are greater than those of corresponding solution of fumaric acid.
- (iv) Densities of maleic acid solutions are smaller than those of fumaric acid solutions.
- (v) Parachor values of both the acids, when compared with the calculated value, show a considerable drop in water.

P calculated = 236 for both the acids. P maleic (observed) = 193 approximately, and P fumaric (observed) = 202 approximately.

Observation (v) is of importance, since it gives a means to use a parachor as a criterion for the distinction between the geometric isomers. The values of parachor obtained by the use of mixture law equations, in the case of above geometric isomers, not only show a considerable drop from the calculated value, but they also show an appreciable difference between the values themselves. For a given equimolar concentration, in general, a 10 unit difference in the values for the two acids has been observed. The two isomers, therefore, can easily be distinguished. A *cis*-isomer possessing a higher dissociation constant gives smaller value than that obtained in the case of *trans*-isomer which possesses higher parachor value due to smaller dissociation constant and hence lesser extent of ionisation.

The parachor data are further supported by the gradations observed in the case of surface tension has been already pointed out under the points (ii), (iii) and (iv) given above. Thus maleic acid can be distinguished from fumaric acid using above criteria.

Section 2—Geometric Isomers in non-aqueous solutions : It is interesting to note that in the non-aqueous solvents the behaviour is opposite to that observed in the case of aqueous solutions, since surface tensions are found to be increasing with the increasing concentrations. Besides this, the following observations can also be made from the Tables 1 and 3 :—

- (i) Relative values for surface tensions of fumaric acid are larger than those of maleic acid.
- (ii) Conductivities of fumaric acid solutions are smaller than those of maleic acid.
- (iii) Densities of fumaric acid solutions are higher than those of maleic acid.
- (iv) Smaller order of parachor drops is observed in non-aqueous solvents than in water.
- (v) Parachor values of fumaric acid are larger than those of maleic acid.

Although the drops in parachor in alcohol are observed but they are not much pronounced. This can be explained in the light of the fact that the dielectric constant of alcohol is much less; compared to that of water (alcohols have value about 25 whereas water has value about 80), so that the ionisation takes place to a very little extent giving rise to smaller drops in parachor due to ionisation. However, maleic acid shows a lesser parachor value in each case i.e., in aqueous as well as in non-aqueous solutions and hence the two can be distinguished. These findings are further supported by the gradation obtained in density, conductivity and surface tension values. It may be noted, however, that the above criterion will be applicable only when the two isomers under consideration, (i) undergo ionisation, (ii) their ionisation constants are widely apart, and (iii) they are appreciably soluble to show a measurable effect on surface tension and hence on parachor value. Slight errors due to presence of impurity etc., may seriously affect the parachor value if solubilities are very small. Since in some cases, the mutual value differences for surface tensions etc., of the order of experimental error have been obtained, whereas in some other cases the value of a given property has been found almost to be the same, Because of these reasons, the method can be used for serving the qualitative purpose only. Further work on a larger number of geometric isomers in various solvents under different conditions may throw more light on this problem.

Section 3—Position Isomers in non-aqueous solvents : Following observations can be made from Tables (1-6) :—

- (i) All the isomeric acids show an increase in the surface tension of the solvents with the increase in the concentration.
- (ii) Parachor values are found to decrease with increasing concentrations for a given equimolar concentration.
- (iii) Conductivity of the solution of an ortho isomer is highest, that of meta isomer is in between and for para isomer it is lowest.
- (iv) Parachor value also shows a gradation but opposite to that observed in the case of conductivities. Parachor of an ortho isomer is least, while that of a para-isomer is highest and the value for a meta isomer lies in between.
- (v) Density and surface tension values also show a gradation. In the case of nitro and hydroxy benzoic acids, meta isomer is found to possess the highest and para the lowest value, while in the case of amino benzoic acids; *p*- isomer possesses the highest and ortho the lowest value.
- (vi) Parachor values for all the three isomers in alcoholic solutions although approach the calculated value but still the gradation is exhibited of the same fashion as pointed out already. In other solvents, parachor value of an ortho isomer shows a drop of about 8-10 units, while for *m* and *p* isomers the calculated values are approached, showing still the gradation.

Since equimolar solutions were to be prepared highest soluble quantity of the least soluble isomer determined the limits of the weights of the isomeric substances to be dissolved in a given quantity of the solvent. It was found that least soluble isomer possesses a very low solubility hence appreciably distinguishable and measurable effects due to three isomers on surface tension and density etc, values, are not obtained. In the present studies, although the mutual value differences for the three isomers are small in magnitude, but still, the gradation in the values of conductivity, surface tension and density is observed in each case, hence these data support the conclusions based on the observations of parachor values.

It can be concluded, therefore, that an idea regarding the distinction between various geometric and position isomers capable of H-bond formation and ionisation can be formed using the observations, based on the parachor surface tension, density and conductivity data, obtained from their equimolar aqueous and non-aqueous solutions.

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